

THE ISSUE IN TEACHING MOLECULAR BIOLOGY IS THE PEDAGOGICAL BASIS FOR THE ORGANIZATION OF EDUCATIONAL AND CREATIVE ACTIVITIES THROUGH THE USE OF EXERCISES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7448574>

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Annotation: *this article covers the pedagogical foundations and methods of organizing educational and creative activities of students through the use of issues and exercises in ensuring the development of students in teaching Molecular Biology in higher educational institutions.*

Key words: *educational-creative activity, knowledge, skills, skills, exercise performance, problem solving, information, thinking, knowledge acquisition.*

The total amount of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and abilities that students receive in a higher educational institution occupies an important place in the study of other disciplines and practical activities, in particular, the study of new information, linking the research problem to the relevant literature. The main task of each teacher is not only to give knowledge to students, but also to instill in him an interest in learning, to teach independent thinking.

The purpose of a number of reforms carried out in the system of higher education today is to improve the quality of knowledge of students studying, to show their abilities, to identify talented students and to create conditions and opportunities for the development of their talent. [1]

In higher educational institutions, the organization of educational creative activities of students, logical thinking of students in education, and the use of issues and exercises in teaching students to organize independent learning will be of paramount importance.

In higher educational institutions, teachers are faced with the question of not only teaching students ready-made lectures, but also teaching students logical and independent thinking, organization of creative research activities, ways to form skills of activity and intelligence in the acquisition of knowledge.[2]

Independent Education based on the results of scientific research is described as follows: independent education is a systematic activity aimed at the formation of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and abilities on the basis of independent assimilation of educational material, tasks with varying degrees of complexity, creative and independent performance of practical tasks in the audience and outside the audience.[1]

All the formation of students' learning skills on the subject being studied, mastering the material to be studied, processing the mastered knowledge, dividing the subject into parts, sequentially mastering the separated parts, comparing it with the newly learned knowledge and previously mastered knowledge, generalizing their knowledge, repeating and their implementation are studied in an independent educational jar. Also, the formation of educational qualifications in the discipline of Molecular Biology in students will be associated with all educational and cognitive activities of students in an independent educational process

Teaching students logical thinking in the study of Molecular Biology will be important in understanding, interpreting biological processes, determining the essence of existing thought. The student understands the interconnection of components in biological systems only when he has the ability to think logically. Logical thinking becomes important in understanding protein biosynthesis in Molecular Biology. Because protein biosynthesis is a matrix synthesis process, it becomes necessary to understand that the stages of the process are interconnected.[3]

It is known that students, when studying the topics of Molecular Biology, try to memorize it if they do not understand the process. Memorizing without understanding the essence of the process causes the information to be quickly forgotten. Forgotten information causes a loss of the quality of knowledge acquired as a result of a loss of systematicity. The use of exercises to identify forgotten information and fill gaps in the knowledge that has arisen causes an increase in the quality of knowledge.

The acquisition of the intended knowledge when it is called the creative approach of students to learning is expressed in the fact that on the basis of their ability to find suitable techniques for learning, to realize their individual characteristics as a result of working on themselves, to create a method convenient for the student to acquire knowledge, to control the level of For this, however, it is important that the student knows

the importance of using issues and exercises to control their knowledge and increase their thinking capacity. The use of issues and exercises serves to improve the logical thinking of students, the acquisition of knowledge, the quality of knowledge. [4]

Creative education is a special aspect of arming students with social experience, it is education aimed at student thinking. It is valid in the shell of the work of the organizational system that stands above it – in the field of student-youth education of society, the creative assimilation of lower organizational systems – information content from itself involves the problems of educating creative abilities in students. The main principle of a systematic approach to pedagogical phenomena is the analysis of the components of the problem, first of all, in the structure of the organizational system that stands above it, and then in relation to the organizational system that stands below it itself, going from general to private. On the contrary, a systematic approach complements a complex approach.

When the components of the problem under study are distinguished in a complex approach, the relationship between components by a systematic approach is analyzed. From the point of view of society, it is an activity suitable for the requirements of creative education, for the needs of educating a perfect person, aimed at prospects, its decision-making, wide distribution among teachers leads to the formation of innovative pedagogical practice, the discovery of new educational systems, principles, tools, organizational forms. Creative activity develops through three types of education on the basis of the formation of such qualities as creative activity of the individual, activity on cognition, organizational activity, and these lead to effective results through unconventional forms and methods of Education.[5]

Creative education is a creative activity with a social value. The next component of the development of educational and creative activities of students is the creative assimilation of information content, and part of it-educational materials. Creative mastering can be compared to non – verbal education.

On the basis of Verbal education lies the memorization of students. It is a memory-oriented education. Creative education is an activity aimed at thinking, consequently, at independent thinking of students, learning by creativity. Mastering is a broad concept, which means integrating one's own experience into the experience of others.

Creative mastering is a component of an organizational system that stands above itself and serves as a component that postpones itself – the conditions for the development of creative abilities. After all, without a complete understanding of the essence of creative mastering, it is impossible to realize the problem of mastering creative abilities. After that, the view of study as a subject of activity made it possible to distinguish a number of principles related to student creativity.[6]

In molecular biology, there are various theoretical and quantitative data, which are necessary for students to know by heart whether it is widely applied in practice, what is common, in order to be able to use them in solving examples and problems, in performing exercises.[7]

The use of issues and exercises in classes to better remember the quantitative data on theories and processes and to control their acquisition brings high efficiency to the surface. In this case, the issue and exercises are used so that the lesson is mainly heuristic and in a way that motivates the search. This means that the control over the assimilation of the material given as an assignment for the independent study of students is carried out together with the students. The issue to be asked encourages an understanding of the content of the issue based on recall questions, together determining which student is ready for a new lesson. In this, the task of the teacher is not to adapt the teaching to the individual abilities of students, but to maximally promote the mental development of all students.

It is also possible that the issue prepared on the basis of the topic is composed of integrated issues, ensuring the continuity and consistency of the topics. The main advantage of such issues is such that it is possible to organize a system of knowledge in students, to help them imagine interdisciplinary connections. Issues require educational and creative activity of each student, so it is necessary to prepare a group for the training. In this, it is advisable to give literature on the topic of the lesson, to summarize practical experience, to focus on concrete phenomena, to promote the development of uniform actions and requirements.

In the formation of initial skills for working issues from molecular biology, students are encouraged to work the issue given in a group manner. Within a certain period of time, students are offered issues that are recorded on the board and the solution is in different options. In finding a solution to the issue, a discussion is organized between groups. During the discussion, good proposals are accepted. The provision of

opportunities to invite, debate, exchange ideas to students in the lesson not only develops his creative thinking and increases student confidence.

Issues related to molecular biology can also be used to determine if a topic has been mastered. In the organization of test classes, well-mastered, educated students of the subject, the heads of each line can be the one who controls the knowledge of students. In this case, after the students have worked out the issue on the topic, the head of the series examines the solution to the issue. The identified error is explained to the students by the head of the series. Students independently carry out the continuation of the issues after the head of the series finds and explains the solution to the issue. The head of the line controls the process and conducts calculations. And the teacher monitors everyone's work.

In conclusion, it can be said that in order to study science, the professor organizes educational and creative activism with the aim of studying new information by the student, by fulfilling the issues given by the teacher to study Molecular Biology. The use of issues and exercises based on a creative approach in the learning process ensures the acquisition of theoretical information, the content of the topic forms the skill of correct expression, allows students to control the knowledge acquired in cognitive acquisition, as well as analyze the knowledge acquired.

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